

The effect of funding for disadvantaged students on academic underachievement

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Summary

1. We study the impact of targeted school funding for disadvantaged pupils in Flemish primary education, where schools with at least 10% disadvantaged students receive additional resources.
2. Using longitudinal data and combining Regression Discontinuity Design with Stochastic Frontier Analysis, we assess both achievement and underachievement.
3. The results show that additional funding does not improve average achievement but significantly reduces underachievement, meaning disadvantaged pupils get closer to reaching their potential.
4. The funding is particularly effective in reducing short-term learning gaps, while long-term underachievement remains more difficult to address.
5. Overall, the policy has narrowed educational inequalities by supporting disadvantaged students in realizing their full capabilities.

1. Introduction

High-performing education systems ensure that all children have access to high-quality learning opportunities. Yet, children from disadvantaged backgrounds often face barriers that place them at higher risk of underachievement and school dropout. These students typically require greater

instructional support, while the schools they attend often have fewer resources to meet their needs. To counter this imbalance, many countries have introduced funding policies that provide additional resources to schools with a larger share of disadvantaged students.

This policy brief summarizes work by Badunenko et al. (2025) in which we examine

the case of Flanders (Belgium), where the “Equal Educational Opportunities” policy grants extra funding to schools with more than 10% disadvantaged pupils. Disadvantage is identified by the Flemish Ministry of Education through socioeconomic indicators such as parental education and household income. Using unique longitudinal data covering Flemish students throughout their six years of primary education, we assess whether this targeted funding has been effective in reducing educational inequalities. Our analysis goes beyond measuring achievement alone. Instead, we also focus on underachievement, understood as the gap between a pupil’s potential and their actual performance. By doing so, we offer new insights into whether additional resources help disadvantaged students reach their full potential.

2. Data and Methodology

Our study uses detailed longitudinal data from Flemish primary education, following pupils from the first until the sixth grade. The dataset, known as *Schoolloopbanen in het Basisonderwijs (SiBO)*, tracked over 6,000 children, with a focus on oversampling disadvantaged students to ensure reliable estimates. For the purpose of our analysis, we rely on a subsample of 2,282 students across 165 schools, observed over six years, resulting in nearly 13,000 observations. The data include standardized mathematics test scores, IQ measures, and rich background information on family circumstances, including parental education, income, and employment status.

To evaluate the effect of targeted funding, we exploit a sharp Regression Discontinuity Design (RDD). The Flemish policy allocates additional resources to schools where at least 10% of students are classified as

disadvantaged, based on official criteria such as parental education or household income support. By comparing schools just above and below this threshold, we are able to identify the causal effect of the funding.

In addition, we employ Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA), an approach that estimates the “achievement frontier” based on pupils’ ability and socioeconomic background. This allows us to assess underachievement, defined as the gap between a pupil’s potential and their actual test scores. By combining RDD and SFA, we measure whether additional funding reduces this underachievement. Importantly, the method also distinguishes between persistent underachievement, which is long-term and harder to remedy, and transient underachievement, which can be more easily addressed through interventions such as tutoring or smaller class sizes.

3. Results

Our findings reveal that additional funding for schools with at least 10% disadvantaged pupils does not significantly affect overall achievement levels in mathematics. However, the policy does reduce underachievement. This means that while average test scores do not rise, disadvantaged pupils come closer to realizing their potential compared to peers in schools that did not receive the extra resources.

The analysis further shows that the policy is particularly effective in addressing transient underachievement, which reflects short-term gaps that can be mitigated through interventions such as remedial teaching or smaller class sizes. Persistent underachievement, by contrast, is less responsive to the funding and remains more difficult to tackle.

Overall, the results suggest that the targeted funding policy has been successful in narrowing the gap between students' expected and actual performance, thereby contributing to more equitable educational outcomes in Flemish primary education.

While we document that the targeted funding policy did not lead to a rise in average achievement scores, we find that this policy significantly reduced underachievement among disadvantaged students. This distinction arises because achievement reflects observed test scores, while underachievement measures the gap between a pupil's potential and their actual performance. Our findings show that pupils in schools that were subject to policy became more efficient in converting their potential into performance, suggesting that additional funding was effective in closing educational gaps.

4. Policy recommendations

Our results highlight the importance of maintaining and refining targeted support measures for disadvantaged students. Since the additional funding reduces underachievement but does not affect overall achievement, policymakers should focus on ensuring that resources are used effectively to help students reach their full potential.

Schools should continue investing additional resources in ways that directly address learning gaps, such as reducing class sizes, providing individualized support, and offering remedial teaching. School leaders should also strengthen monitoring systems to identify underachievers early and intervene before problems become persistent.

Education authorities should maintain policies that target disadvantaged groups,

while also improving the allocation formula to account for the intensity of disadvantage rather than a single threshold. Monitoring both achievement and underachievement provides a more complete picture of policy effectiveness and should become a standard evaluation tool.

The European Union can support Member States by promoting knowledge sharing on targeted funding schemes and by financing research that evaluates not only achievement but also underachievement. Encouraging evidence-based policies across countries will help ensure that resources effectively reduce inequalities in education.

Finally, we observe that additional funding alone is not sufficient to lift overall achievement but is valuable in helping disadvantaged pupils approach their potential. A continued commitment to targeted, evidence-based funding mechanisms—combined with close monitoring at multiple levels—can foster more equitable educational systems.

What is BRIDGE ?

BRIDGE is an impact-driven project that aims to build resilient individuals through effective educational transition by formulating robust policy recommendations on education and training policies, the efficient use of public resources and the support of equity and inclusion in education and training systems in the EU.

Further Information:

Badunenko, O., Mazrekaj, D., Kumbhakar, S. C., & De Witte, K. (2025). The effect of funding for disadvantaged students on academic underachievement. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 12(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-025-05524-1>

**Funded by
the European Union**

BRIDGE is funded by the European Commission in its **Horizon Europe** framework (grant 101177154). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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